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Politics of Nigerian Newspaper Coverage of Ondo State 2012 Gubernatorial Election

Ikenna Timothy ASOMBA and S. Olasunkanmi AROWOLO

Abstract

Elections is *sine-qua-non* to democracy. The coverage of elections has been a major sensitive part of journalism. Journalists are expected to avoid sentiments and be as objective as possible in reporting elections. The relationship between politics and the media is therefore an inextricable one. Thus, the media go through 'an arduous task' to give effective coverage as they did in the October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial election which saw the emergence of Dr. Rahman Olusegun Mimiko of Labour Party (LP) as winner of the poll. This makes him to be the first Governor of Ondo State to be returned through the ballot box. Hence, this study finds out how Nigerian newspapers reported the October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial election. The study also views the reportage by some selected newspapers in the light of ownership interest and political affiliation as it affects their objectivity and editorial independence. The study content analysed 15 days (30 editions) – a week before the election, the Election Day and a week after the election (Sunday, June 14, 2014- Sunday, June 28, 2014) of *The Nation* and the *Nigeria Compass* Newspapers. The newspapers were carefully chosen based on their ownership structure and political affiliation. Agenda Setting and Social Responsibility theories of mass communication formed the theoretical framework. Findings from the study shows *The Nation* and *Nigeria Compass* were sensational in their reports, politics of calumny and hate were held supreme during the period under review, thus indicating that owners/proprietors influence editorial contents, thus tampering with the editorial independence and objectivity in the newsroom.

Keywords: Politics, Ondo, Election, Nigeria, Newspapers, *The Nation*, *Nigeria Compass*, Agenda Setting, Social Responsibility Theories, Journalists.

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Introduction

Before 1922, elective positions were occupied and controlled by the British colonialists, but the 1922 Clifford Constitution marked a watershed in the Nigerian political terrain, as Nigerians were now given the opportunity to be voted for in the House of Parliament. Dating back 1960, when the country gained independence from the British colonialists, it has witnessed the evolution of various systems of government which included parliamentary, military, presidential and now democratic system of government.

In a democratic society, elections are mostly the conventional means of promoting some citizens to positions of leadership in the republic. Like the Presidential elections, the gubernatorial elections are vigorous as they determine who is selected as the chief executive of state and to whom the majority of people in the state would entrust guardianship of their sovereignty (Lindberg, 2006). As a result, gubernatorial campaigns and election attract interest of reporters and gain considerable focus of the news media. Obviously, few citizens personally attend political-campaign rallies. Most people depend on other sources of information. So, voters receive many of the messages about the candidates not directly from the candidates but from the news media (Ridout & Mellen, 2007).

Correspondingly, newspapers are an important source where readers can find reports of pre-election campaigns, election and post-election activities. Newspapers serve as a key source of issue knowledge for voters in election campaigns (Benoit, 2007). Newspapers perform more successfully at informing voters than television news, candidate advertising and radio because “for national political news coverage, the most thorough, comprehensive, and substantive information regarding political campaigns, political issues, and public policies is available to readers of comprehensive large city daily papers (Hollihan, 2001, p. 79).

It is in recognition of this powerful role newspapers play in shaping agenda for the people that Oso (2006) stated that before now, newspaper ownership was closely linked to party politics, noting that many notable politicians, Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe, Chief Obafemi Awolowo, Herbert Macaulay, Sessei Ikoli, Lateef Jakande, Bisi Onabanjo were either journalists and/or newspaper proprietors. The involvement of the press in party politics and electioneering started with the Legislative Council Election under the 1922 Clifford Constitution. The three Lagos seats in the

1938 legislative elections were fought by the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) and the Union of Young Nigerians (UYN). Many of the newspaper owners-editors were involved in the formation of the two parties.

The NNDP was formed by Herbert Macaulay and Thomas Jackson who owned the *Lagos Weekly Record* while Ernest Sessei Ikoli was closely associated with the formation of UYN.

The press was actively involved in the heated campaigns for the elections. Some newspapers were established purposely to fight the elections thus introducing bitterness and vehemence into electioneering campaigns.

According to Omu (1978:233) as cited in Oso (2006), from 1920s when elections into Legislative House started, “newspapers shifted their focus from that of political group supporters to organs of the political parties.”

The expansion in the newspaper industry coincided with the constitutional changes which gradually devolved formal political power to the educated and business elite. Apart from Zik who used the *West African Pilot* to create “a political following... which was channeled into the NCNC, the *Daily Service* became the official organ of the Action Group (AG) when it was formed” (Grant, 1975, p. 100). The paper was later renamed *Daily Express* in 1960 when the AG and Lord Thompson of Britain came together to form the *Allied Newspaper of Nigeria* in 1958. Awolowo had the *Nigerian Tribune* which was also linked to the AG.

In the North, the Northern People's Congress (NPC) formed in 1949 later took over the Hausa language newspaper, *Gaskiya Ta fi Kwabo* and its English language counterpart, *Nigerian Citizen* (later *New Nigeria*) to advocate, defend and advance its interest. As the various parties gained power in the regions and at the centre, they established newspapers funded from public treasury but meant to defend parochial personal or party interests. The Federal Government under the NPC established the *Morning Post* and *Sunday Post* while the Eastern Region (under NCNC) had the *Eastern Outlook*. The North consolidated its control on *Gaskiya Ta fi Kwabo* and the *Nigerian Citizen*, and in 1964 Akintola established the *Daily Sketch* in the Western Region as the propaganda organ of his unpopular NNDP Government (different from Herbert Macaulay's NNDP referred to above). These papers performed the functions of the former party newspapers to

complement them. In a space of four years after independence, government/party newspaper was the dominant form of ownership. The government also had control of radio and television.

Howbeit, Oso (ibid) opined that the Second Republic also saw the re-emergence of party-affiliated or politician-owned newspapers in the country. From 1979 to 1983, many politicians established newspapers to propagate and defend their political positions. One of the most notable of such newspapers was the *National Concord* and *Sunday Concord* founded in March 1980 by Chief M.K.O. Abiola, who was then a prominent member of the ruling National Party of Nigeria (NPN). Other papers of the period included *The Trumpet* owned by Jim Nwobodo, the then Nigerian People's Party (NPP) Governor of old Anambra State; *The Democrat* owned by a group of Northern politicians and businessmen; *The Advocate* based in Ibadan owned by Chief Adisa Akinloye and others.

All these papers like their older counterparts, like the Nigerian Tribune were more or less megaphones of their owners and their political parties. What Dr. Dele Ogunade said of the *Concord* could be true of the rest. According to him, the paper "was a shrill, invective politically partisan paper that was more of an embarrassment to the fine crop of professionals who wrote and edited it" (African Concord, October 8, 1990).

Many journalists lost their professional sense in a bid to out-do their so-called opponents and satisfy their paymasters. The 1983 elections Oso (op cit) said "saw the worst of Nigerian journalism. Every known and respected canon of the profession was thrown to the dogs. The mass media were simply seen by politicians and journalists as veritable instruments to wage electoral war fare. Mass media were used to mobilize electoral support on ethnic and regional basis as was the case during the first republic. Nevertheless, Cohen (1963:13) commented that newspapers "may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about." While the news may not determine what the people should think, the news suggests which issue is salient and tells people that such an issue is something they should be thinking about (McCombs & Shaw, 1972).

Ondo History, Politics and Elections

Ondo State, Nigeria was created on 3 February 1976 from the former Western State. It originally included what is now Ekiti State, which was

split off in 1996. Akure is the state capital. The state is named after the ancient city of Ondo and in present day Nigeria, it's one of the six States making up the South-West geo-political zone. Ondo State consists eighteen Local Government Areas, which include Akoko North-East headquarters in Ikare, Akoko North-West, Akoko South-East, Akoko South-West, Akure North, Akure South, Ese Odo, Idanre, Ifedore, Ilaje, Ile Oluji/Okeigbo, Irele, Odigbo, Okitipupa, Ondo East, Ondo West, Ose and Owo.

The majority of the state's citizens live in urban centers. The big government universities in Ondo state are the Federal University of Technology, Akure and the Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba/Akoko. Adeyemi College of Education in Ondo is a degree awarding institution affiliated to the Obafemi Awolowo University Ile-Ife. There is also the newly established Ondo State University of Science and Technology Okitipupa and private tertiary institutions like Achievers University, Owo, Rufus Giwa Polytechnic, Owo and Wesley University, Ondo

Ondo State is bounded in the East by Edo State, in the North by Kogi State, in the West by Osun and Ogun States and in the South by the Atlantic Ocean. Agriculture (including fishing) constitutes the main occupation of the people of the state.

Ondo State is said to be the largest cocoa producing state, in Nigeria. Other agricultural products include yams, cassava and palm produce. Ondo State is a multi-ethnic state with the majority being Yorubas while there are also *Arogbos* and *Akpois* who are of Ijaw extraction and are mostly located in the riverine areas of the state, while a sizable number of the Ondo State people who speak a variant of the Yoruba language similar to Ife dialect reside in Oke-Igbo. These people are also Yorubas.

Ondo State contains the largest number of public schools in Nigeria - over 880 primary schools and 190 secondary schools. The State is also one of the oil producing Niger Delta states in Nigeria with abundant Bitumen deposit in the Southern part of the State ranked one of the largest in the world.

In the 36 years existence of the State, it has had 12 Military administrators and six democratically elected representatives as Governors. In all it has had 18 Governors with only Governor Olusegun Mimiko breaking the political jinx by returning for a second time through the ballot box. Thus,

the list: Military Governor, Ita David Ikpeme (3 Feb 1976 - 24 Jul 1978); Military Governor, Sunday Tuoyo (24 July, 1978- 1 October, 1979).

When the Obasanjo administration handed over to civilian government on October 1, 1979, elections conducted in Ondo State, saw Pa Michael Adegunle Ajasin of the United Party of Nigeria (UPN) emerged the first democratically elected Governor in Ondo State. Pa Ajasin, was at the helms of affairs for four years, between (October 1, 1979- October 1983), when Governor Akin Omoboriowo of the ruling National Party of Nigeria (NPN) emerged winner of the polls.

Governor Omoboriowo, the second democratically elected governor of Ondo State, didn't stay up to three months on seat, when the Military struck, overthrowing the Alhaji Shehu Shagari's presidential administration. As the elections were reportedly marred by violence and allegations of widespread vote rigging and electoral malfeasance, leading to legal battles over the results, Major General Muhammadu Buhari, who became the central head of state and leader of the Supreme Military Council (SMC) struck against this backdrop.

Consequently, Military Governor, Michael Bamidele Otiko, emerged chief executive of the state between (January 1984- 2 September 1985). When the Buhari government was peacefully overthrown by the SMC's third-ranking member, General Ibrahim Badamosi Babangida (IBB) in August 1985 over purported misuse of power, violations of human rights by key officers of the SMC, and the government's failure to deal with the country's deepening economic crisis, Military Governor, Michael Akhigbe came to the helms of affairs between (2 September, 1985 – 26 August, 1986).

Other Military Governors that followed suit were Ekundayo B. Opaleye (26 August 1986 - 17 Dec 1987); Raji Alagbe Rasabi (17 December 1987 - July 1988); the erstwhile embattled Nigerian Ports Authority Chairman, Chief Olabode George (July 1988 - 3 September 1990) and Sunday Abiodun Olukoya (3 September, 1990 - 3 January, 1992).

Following IBB's consent to conduct election in 1992, Dele Olumilua of Moshood Kashimawo Olawale Abiola's (MKO) Social Democratic Party (SDP) emerged Governor of the state in the interim central regime of Chief Ernest Shonekan that between (3 January 1992 - November 1993), when the Military swoop into action again.

As Shonekan was to rule in the Babangida's Transitional Council, until elections scheduled for February 1994, Defense Minister of his regime, Sanni Abacha forced Shonekan's resignation on November 17, 1993. Abacha had justified that Shonekan was unable to reverse Nigeria's economic problems and to defuse lingering political tension and with the country reportedly sliding into chaos, Abacha dissolved all democratic institutions and replaced elected governors with military officers.

Thus, Military Governors that ruled Ondo state between 1993 until 1998 when Abacha died included L. Mike Torey (9 December 1993 - 19 September 1994); Ahmed Usman (19 September, 1994 - 22 August, 1996); Anthony Ibe Onyearugbulem (22 August 1996 - August 1998).

When Abacha died of heart failure on June 8, 1998 and was replaced by General Abdulsalami Abubakar, Moses Fasanya became the last Military Governor, as he ruled Ondo state between (August 1998 - May 1999), when Abubakar handed over power to a democratically elected civilian government, which saw former military head of state, Olusegun Obasanjo, who was just freed from prison by Abubakar, ran as a civilian candidate and won the presidential election under the platform of the ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP).

Consequently, as Ondo is a south-western state, a region which till date is a strong base for predominantly Yoruba parties, Chief Adebayo Ade Adefarati of Alliance for Democracy (AD) became the fourth democratically elected Governor of Ondo State. Adefarati governed the state between (29 May, 1999 - 29 May, 2003).

After four years, when another election was conducted, Chief Olusegun Agagu of the ruling People's Democratic Party (PDP) was announced winner by the electoral umpire, the Independent Electoral Commission (INEC), in the keenly contested polls. He steered the affairs of the state for another four years between (29 May 2003, - 29 May, 2007).

In the 2007 election, which saw Alhaji Umaru Yar'Adua and Dr. Goodluck Jonathan, both of the People's Democratic Party (PDP), elected President and Vice President, respectively, Agagu was again announced winner by INEC. Howbeit, as other candidates and international observers, alleged that the general election was marred by electoral fraud, Mr. Rahman

Olusegun Mimiko of the Labour Party headed to the Election Tribunal and subsequently to the Appeal Tribunal to reclaim his mandate. It was on Friday, July 25, 2008, that the Tribunal sitting in Akure annulled the election of Governor Olusegun Agagu and declared Mimiko as the winner of the election, thus, the legitimate sixth democratically elected Governor of the Sunshine state. With the reclaiming of this mandate, Mimiko was sworn in as Ondo State Governor on 24 February, 2009. He therefore governed till February 24, 2013.

The October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial Election

According to the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), Saturday, 20th October 2012 was approved as the date for the 2012 Ondo State governorship election. The time-table and schedule of activities released by the Commission at the end of its meeting on 3rd April, 2012 shows that the notice of the election will be issued on 16th July while the collection of forms for the election by political parties at INEC headquarters will be on 27th July 2012.

The Commission stated that campaigns by political parties in public will begin on 12th July 2012 and end on 19th October 2012, a day before the governorship election is conducted. Tony Momoh in Edetaen Ojo (2007) said this provision is in tandem with sections 101 (1) of the 2006 Electoral Act as amended.

Tied to this, INEC mandated all political parties sponsoring candidates for the election, to submit the names of their (party) agents to the Resident Electoral Commissioner (REC) Ondo state, on the 13th October 2012, seven days to the election.

Thirteen political parties and candidates registered to contest the election. They included: Oluwarotimi Odunayo Akeredolu of Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN); Adeuti Stephen Taiye of (ACPN); Adeyemi Bolarinwa of All Nigerian People's Party (ANPP); Oladimeji Tokumboh Adegoroye of (APS); Olagsegiri Gbenga Festus of (BNPP); Builder Omoyele Afolabi Olorunwa of (CAP) and Ehinlanwo Olusoji of Congress for Progressive Change (CPC).

Others were Rahman Olusegun Mimiko of Labour Party (LP); Oladipo Bolade Lawrence of National Conscience Party (NCP); Abikanlu James Olusola of (NSDP); Victor Oluwafemi Adetusin of (PDC); Alex Olusola

Oke of People's Democratic Party (PDP) and Omoreggha Olatunji Kris of (PPA).

However, countdown to the election, it was observed that the media sidelined the other political parties and their candidates, thereby given prominence to three major political parties and their candidates, as if they were the only contenders to the coveted seat. The ACN candidate, Rotimi Akeredolu; PDP candidate, Olusola Oke and the Labour Party man, Olusegun Mimiko, enjoyed media coverage ahead of their counterparts in the race.

Howbeit, in their review of studies regarding agenda setting theory, Weaver, McCombs, and Shaw (2004) as well as Allen and Casey (2007) found a generally positive correlation between media agendas and public agendas. Thus, the news can both inform the public and influence public perceptions of which issues are most important.

Such insights into the potential of newspaper coverage to influence public knowledge and perceptions of developmental issues like elections justify the need to carry out this study on how two dailies- The Nation and Nigerian Compass covered the October 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial elections.

Statement of Problem

Coverage of elections has been a major function of journalism. Most media houses take their journalists through refresher courses on reporting elections because of the sensitive nature of election in the development of a democratic dispensation.

Journalists are expected to shun sentiments and be objective as possible in reporting elections. The relationship between politics and the media is therefore an inseparable one. The media went through strenuous task to give effective coverage to the October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial election, which saw the emergence of Dr. Rahman Olusegun Mimiko of Labour Party (LP) as winner of the poll.

This perhaps makes him to be the first Governor of Ondo State to be returned through the ballot box, even though suits were filed against him shortly after the elections by the opposition parties of Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN) and the People's Democratic Party (PDP) candidate,

Olusola Oke, in the Election Tribunal, challenging his victory.

This research thus, aims to find out how Nigerian newspapers reported the October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial election. The study thus, views this reportage by some selected newspapers in the light of ownership interest and political affiliation as it affects their objectivity and editorial independence.

Research questions

This study analyse the report of the October 20, 2012 Ondo Gubernatorial election. The questions are:

1. What prominence is given to the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election by the selected newspapers?
2. What is the tone of reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election by the selected newspapers?
3. What is the major source of the news stories about the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election in the selected newspapers?
4. Who are the major players covered in the selected newspapers' reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election?
5. To what extent did the ownership structure and political affiliation of the selected newspapers influence the reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial elections?

Theoretical Framework

Since the primary objective of this study is to examine how proprietors and their political affiliation/partisanship affects the editorial independence of the mass media, whilst encouraging development communication in the practice of journalism, the study will be anchored on the Agenda Setting Theory of Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw (1972) and the Social Responsibility Theory of Siebert et al (1956).

Agenda Setting Theory

Initially, the agenda setting theory was understood in a relatively straightforward way. Agenda setting as laid out by Maxwell McCombs and Donald Shaw was that "agenda-setting is the process whereby the news media lead the public in assigning relative importance to various public issues. The agenda setting hypothesis came about when researchers

became dissatisfied with the dominant theoretical position in mass communication research during the 1950s and the 1960s- the limited effects model. Joseph Klapper stated in his book *Effect of Mass Communication* in 1960 when he wrote:

“Mass communication ordinarily does not serve as a necessary and sufficient cause of audience effects, but rather functions among and through a nexus of mediating factors and influences.”

For many years, the approach used in communication research was to look for attitude change and most of the research had found that the mass media have little effect in this area. However, researchers were looking at the wrong target. May be the mass media had their effects on people's perceptions-their views of the world-rather than their attitudes. The media agenda influences the public agenda not by saying this issue is important in an overt way but by giving more space and time to that issue and by giving it more prominent space and time. That is, if headlines of newspapers and lead stories of television newscasts all highlight a study. The assumptions or principles of this theory as stated by McCombs and Shaw, 1973 cited in (Memedu), 1999 are:

1. The mass media, such as the press, do not reflect social reality because news is filtered, chosen and shaped by newsroom staff or broadcasters.
2. People get their news from limited sources because people do not pay attention to all outlets; thus they rest on the mass media.
3. Few media agenda, which were chosen by professional gatekeepers, lead people to perceive given issues as important.

Cohen (1963:13) as cited in Daramola (2012:85) draws home the agenda setting power of the press when he said:

The press may not be successful much of the time in telling people what to think, but they are stunningly successful in telling them what to think about (Daramola, 2012:85).

Daramola (2012: ibid) said Severin and Tankard (1997) in citing researcher Norton Long (1958) who had for long attempted to explain the agenda-setting function of the press when he wrote:

In a sense, the newspaper is the prime mover in setting the

territorial agenda. It has a great part in determining what most people will be talking about, what most people will think the facts are and what people will regard as the way problems are to be dealt with.

Daramola (ibid) argued that the quotations clearly illustrate the agenda setting power of the mass media, noting that when the press seizes a great issue to thrust unto the agenda of talk, it moves action on its own. This he said describes the ability of the media to influence the salience of events in the public mind.

In other words, the media decide what they think should be on the priority consideration of people. They set the tone and fix rules, making certain issues to predominate discussions at all cost for, as well as determining when in their view, society has had enough, and so it should be called off while they introduce another issue.

Agenda-setting studies have developed evidences that the press selects certain issues to play up at times when they are not significant in the public mind and they then become part of the accepted agenda. No wonder it is said that the press has the ability to mentally order and organize the world for people.

Social Responsibility Media Theory

The central focus of this theory is that the media in Nigeria today should not be allowed to be concentrated in the hands of political bigwigs, multinational business conglomerates and advertisers to the disadvantage of the generality of the people. According to Folarin (1998:27), the politicians and the money bags have used their resources to hijack the mass media thus using them to advance their personal political and business ambitions, while they limit media access to other citizens who may have an idea to express.

The media have therefore become slavish to few opportunists who have used them to for personnel advantage at the expense of the people of pressing social concerns such as right of women, children and minorities. In order to checkmate this unfortunate trend and make the media socially responsible, the media should be kept to certain social standards whilst at the same time, ensuring preservation of press freedom (Owolabi & Achike, 2011, in Journalism and Society)

Nwosu (1996) said that the press in any country should be responsible in the performance of its functions. The theory recommends six specific functions for the press as captured by (Siebert et al and Kunezick). These include:

“Servicing the political system by providing information, discussion and debate on public affairs, enlightening the public so as to make it capable of self-government, Safeguarding the rights of the individual by serving as a watchdog against government; servicing the economic system, primarily by bringing together the buyers and sellers of goods and services through the medium of advertising as well as providing entertainment and maintaining its self-sufficiency so as to be free from the pressures of special interest (Siebert et al 1956:74, Kunezick 1988:42).

The nucleus of the social responsibility theory is the traditional role of the media as the watchdog of the society, disseminating fair, objective and balanced information without hindrance. It is on this premise that Awolowo (1958:176) as cited by Owolabi & Achike (2006) charged media practitioners to always stand on the side of democracy because without democracy, there can be neither liberty for the citizen nor freedom for the press. For the media to be seen above board, it must carry out its responsibilities without fear or favour and without discrimination.

Scope and methodology

This study covers all editions of *Nigerian Compass* and *The Nation* newspapers published from October 14, 2012 through October 28, 2012, thus taking into account the pre-election, election and post-election activities. This period is two weeks, because this was when reports about the election became intensified. Therefore, about fifteen (15) editions each of the newspapers are being examined, totaling thirty (30) editions in all. All related stories within this period shall be analyzed and related stories before or after the period will be excluded.

Purposive sampling was adopted to select the two newspapers of the whole avalanche of population of daily national newspapers in Nigeria. They were purposively chosen, considering measures as ownership structure and political partisanship/affiliation. This is to establish if the two factors affected the newspapers treatment of the election.

Data analysis and discussion

Table 1: Number of Stories Published on Ondo State October 20, 2012 Gubernatorial Election

NEWSPAPERS	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
<i>THE NATION</i>	127	55.2
<i>NIGERIAN COMPASS</i>	103	44.8
TOTAL	230	100

Table 1 shows that a total of two hundred and thirty (230) stories were published by the two newspapers on the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election. Of this number, *The Nation* had the largest share of one hundred and twenty-seven (127) stories representing 55.2 per cent, while the *Nigerian Compass* had one hundred and three (103) stories representing 44.8 per cent.

The research based on the data displayed in table 1 above, showed that *The Nation* reported the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election more than the *Nigerian Compass*. This is evidenced in the 127 stories, *The Nation* published on the election. Consequently, on the ordered scale, *The Nation* reported the election most frequently than the *Nigerian Compass*.

Table 2: Daily Newspapers Reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 Gubernatorial Election

Day	<i>The Nation</i>	<i>Nigerian Compass</i>	Total	Percentage (%)
OCTOBER 14	6	3	9	3.9
OCTOBER 15	11	1	12	5.2
OCTOBER 16	14	6	20	8.7
OCTOBER 17	11	6	17	7.4
OCTOBER 18	13	8	21	9.1
OCTOBER 19	17	18	35	15.2
OCTOBER 20	15	13	28	12.2
OCTOBER 21	11	4	15	6.5
OCTOBER 22	7	4	11	4.8
OCTOBER 23	5	7	12	5.2
OCTOBER 24	5	6	11	4.8
OCTOBER 25	6	13	19	8.3
OCTOBER 26	2	10	12	5.2
OCTOBER 27	1	1	2	0.9
OCTOBER 28	3	3	6	2.6
TOTAL	127	103	230	100

Table 2 shows the daily distribution of news report of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election with October 19 having the highest number with thirty-five (35) stories, representing 15.2 per cent, while October 27 had the least with just 2 stories representing 0.9 per cent.

It can be further deduced that *The Nation* had an average of nine (9) stories per day, that is the total number of stories published (127) divided by the number of days covered (15) (i.e. $127/15= 8.46$ approximately 9), while *Nigerian Compass* published an average of seven (7) stories per day, that is the total number of stories published (103) divided by the number of days covered (15) (i.e $103/15= 6.87$ approximately 7).

From the foregoing, it can also be deduced that an average of 15 stories were published daily on the October 20, 2012 Ondo State gubernatorial election by the two newspapers, that is the total number of stories published (230) divided by the number of days (15) (i.e $230/15= 15$).

RQ1: What prominence is given to the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election by the selected newspapers?

Position of Stories

POSITION	<i>The Nation</i>	<i>Nigerian Compass</i>	TOTAL
FRONT PAGE	19 (15%)	15 (15%)	34 (15%)
INSIDE PAGES	94 (74%)	75 (73%)	169 (73%)
BACK PAGE	5 (4%)	-----	5 (2.2%)
OTHERS	9 (7%)	13 (13%)	22 (10%)
TOTAL	127 (100%)	103 (100%)	230 (100%)

Table 3 above shows that 34 stories were published on the front page representing 15 per cent of the total stories published by *The Nation* and *Nigerian Compass* newspapers. The inside page had 169 stories of the total stories published in the two newspapers within the study period, representing 73 per cent. Of the total stories, 5 stories representing 2.2 per cent were published on the back page, while 22 stories, representing 10 per cent was published on other pages.

From the foregoing, of the total stories published by *The Nation* newspaper, 19 stories representing 15 per cent made the paper's front page, while 15 stories, also representing 15 per cent made *Nigerian Compass* front page.

Thus, *The Nation* had more stories on its front page than *Nigerian Compass*.

The Nation also has more stories on the inside page than *Nigerian Compass*. While *The Nation* had 94 stories representing 74 per cent, *Nigerian Compass* had 75 stories representing 75 per cent.

On the back page, *The Nation* also beat *Nigerian Compass* to the number of stories. While *The Nation* had 5 stories representing 4 per cent, *Nigerian Compass* had none.

However, *Nigerian Compass* had more stories on other page than *The Nation*. While *The Nation* had 9 stories representing 7 per cent, *Nigerian Compass* had 13 stories, representing 13 per cent.

From the foregoing, we can aptly answer research question one on what prominence was given to the October 20, 2012 Ondo State gubernatorial election by the two selected newspapers. It can thus be deduced that the October 20, 2012 Ondo State gubernatorial election was given prominence by the two newspapers. Nonetheless, *The Nation* had more stories on the front page than *Nigerian Compass*.

RQ2: What is the tone of reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election by the selected newspapers?

Tone of Story

TONE	<i>The Nation</i>	<i>Nigerian Compass</i>	TOTAL
POSTIVE	29 (22.8%)	20 (19.4%)	49 (21.3%)
NEGATIVE	34 (26.8%)	30 (29.1%)	64 (27.8%)
NEUTRAL	28 (22.1%)	19 (18.5%)	47 (20.4%)
SENSATIONAL	36 (28.4%)	34 (33.01%)	70 (30.4%)
TOTAL	127 (100%)	103 (100%)	230 (100%)

Most of the stories published were in the sensational tone which accounted for a total of 70 stories representing 30.4 per cent, the negative tone follows with 64 stories, representing about 28 per cent (27.8%). The positive tone has a total of 49 stories representing slightly above 21 per cent (21.3%), while the neutral tone has a total of 47 stories representing a little above 20 per cent (20.4%).

In *The Nation*, the sensational tone has the highest number of stories with

36 stories, representing 28.4 per cent of its total published stories. This was followed by the negative tone with 34 stories representing about 27 per cent (26.8%). While the positive tone had a total of 29 stories representing about 23 per cent (22.8%), the neutral tone was the least with 28 stories representing slightly above 22 per cent (22.1%).

Similarly, in the Nigerian Compass, the sensational tone topped the table with 34 stories representing slightly above 33 per cent (33.01%). The negative tone followed with 30 stories representing slightly above 29 per cent (29.11%). Positive tone had 20 stories representing 19.4 per cent, even as neutral tone was the least with a total number of 19 stories representing about 19 per cent (18.5%).

From the foregoing, The Nation had more stories with sensational tone than the Nigerian Compass. While The Nation had 36 stories representing 28.4 per cent, Nigerian Compass had 34 stories representing slightly above 33 per cent (33.01%).

Also, The Nation had more stories with positive, negative and neutral tones than Nigerian Compass. Thus, Positive- The Nation with 29 stories (22.8%), Nigerian Compass with 20 stories (19.4%); Negative- The Nation with 34 stories (26.8%), Nigerian Compass with 30 stories (29.1%) and Neutral- The Nation with 28 stories (22.1%), Nigerian Compass with 19 stories representing about 19 per cent (18.5%).

In answer to research question five on what extent did ownership structure and political affiliation influence the report? This can be deduced from the tone of the story. The Nation, owned by the national leader of Action Congress of Nigeria (ACN), Ashiwaju Bola Ahmed Tinubu had 36 stories representing 28.4 per cent in the sensational tone, in support of the ACN candidate, Oluwarotimi Odunayo Akeredolu (A.K.A Aketi).

Of this number, the paper's sensational tone was highly against the policies, campaign strategies and especially against the personality of the incumbent governor, Dr. Rahman Olusegun Mimiko, who contested under the platform of Labour Party (LP).

Next to the sensational tone was the negative tone with 34 stories representing 26.8 per cent, as against its neutral tone with 28 stories representing 22.1 per cent.

By this statistics, *The Nation* used its negative tone to heavily berate and discredit the policies, campaign strategies and the personality of Mimiko of LP. By the paper's positive tone which makes up 29 stories representing 22.8 per cent, it gave support for the ACN candidate, Akeredolu. Meanwhile, by the paper's neutral tone which makes up 28 stories representing 22.1 per cent, the least of its total published stories, it was indifferent to the candidates, especially between ACN candidate, Akeredolu and LP candidate, Mimiko, whom were observed from the study to be given more coverage as major contenders.

The Nigerian Compass, owned by Otunba Gbenga Daniel, a chieftain of the People's Democratic Party, had 34 stories representing 33.01 per cent in the sensational tone, largely in support of the PDP candidate, Alex Olusola Oke. The paper's sensational tone of this number was highly against the campaign strategies and personality of the ACN candidate, Akeredolu.

Just like *The Nation*, next to *Nigerian Compass* sensational tone was the negative tone with 30 stories representing 29.1 per cent, as against its neutral tone with 19 stories representing 18.5 per cent.

By this statistics, the *Nigerian Compass* used its negative tone to heavily berate and discredit especially the candidate of ACN, Akeredolu, which it saw as a major foe.

By the paper's positive tone which makes up 20 stories representing 19.4 per cent, it gave immense support for the PDP candidate, Oke and slightly support for the LP candidate, Mimiko. Meanwhile, by the paper's neutral tone which makes up 19 stories representing 18.5 per cent, the least of the total published stories, it was indifferent to the candidates, especially on the coverage given Oke, Akeredolu and Mimiko.

In analyzing the nature of stories published, the units of analysis were advocacy, informative, educative and others. The findings are presented in the table below.

RQ3: What is the major source of the news stories about the Ondo State

October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election in the selected newspapers?

Source of Story

SOURCE	<i>The Nation</i>	<i>Nigerian Compass</i>	TOTAL
Coverage/Occurrence	22 (17.3%)	30 (29.13%)	52 (22.6%)
Press Release/Statement	35 (28%)	40 (39%)	75 (32.6%)
Interview	10 (8%)	12 (12%)	22 (9.6%)
Reporter's Analysis	11 (9%)	5 (5%)	16 (7%)
Research Findings/Report	4 (3.2%)	10 (10%)	14 (6.1%)
Investigation	9(7.1%)	2(2%)	1(4.8%)
Other Media Publications/News Agency	2(2%)	3(3%)	5(2.2%)
No Source Indicated	19(15%)	1(1%)	20(8.7%)
Others	15(12%)	-	15(6.5%)
TOTAL	127(100%)	103(100%)	230(100%)

From the above table, the major source of stories published was press release/statements with a total of 75 stories representing about 33 per cent (32.6%). This was followed by coverage/occurrence with a total of 52 stories representing about 23 per cent (22.6%). Interview, no source indicated, reporter's analysis, other research findings/ report, investigation and other media publications/news agency followed suit.

While 22 stories representing about 10 per cent (9.6) was sourced through interview, 20 stories with no source indicated, representing about 9 per cent (8.7%) were published. Also, while 16 stories representing 7 per cent were reporter's analysis, 15 stories representing about 7 per cent (6.5%) were others.

Nonetheless, while 14 stories representing slightly above 6 per cent (6.1%) were sourced through research findings/report, stories sourced through investigation and other media publications/news agency were 15 and 5, representing a minimal 4.8 percent and 2.2 per cent respectively.

In *The Nation* stories sourced through press release/statements had the highest number with a total of 35 stories, representing 28 per cent. This is followed by coverage/occurrence with 22 stories representing slightly above 17 per cent (17.3%).

Stories with no source indicated followed with 19 stories representing 15 per cent, while others followed next with 15 stories representing 12 per cent.

Stories sourced through reporter's analysis followed with 11 stories representing a percent, while stories sourced through investigation followed next with a story representing slightly about 7 percent (7.1%).

In the same vein, while stories sourced through research findings or reports were for stories representing slightly above 3 percent (3.2%), stories sourced through other media publication or news agency bottomed the table with just 2 stories representing a meager 2 percent.

Just like *The Nation*, *Nigerian Compass* sourced the highest number of its stories, through press release/statements with 40 stories representing 39 per cent of its total published stories.

Similarly, stories sourced through interview, research findings or report, reporter's analysis, other media publications/ news agency, investigation and no source indicated followed suit with 12 stories (12 per cent), 10 stories (10 per cent), 5 stories (5 per cent), 3 stories (3 per cent), 2 stories (2 per cent), and 1 story (1 per cent) respectively.

However, the *Nigerian Compass* didn't source stories through others unlike *The Nation* that had 15 stories as indicated in the table above.

Inferentially, the *Nigerian Compass* had more stories sourced through press release/statements and coverage/occurrence than *The Nation*. For the former, while *Nigerian Compass* had 40 stories representing 39 per cent, *The Nation* had 35 stories representing 28 per cent. For the latter, while *Nigerian Compass* had 30 stories, representing slightly above 29 per cent (29.13%), *The Nation* had 22 stories representing slightly above 17 per cent (17.3%).

Similarly, the *Nigerian Compass* had more stories sourced through interview and research findings/report than *The Nation*. For the former, while *Nigerian Compass* had 12 stories representing 12 per cent, *The Nation* fell short with 10 stories representing just 8 per cent. For the latter, while *Nigerian Compass* had 10 stories representing 10 per cent, *The Nation* had 4 stories representing slightly above 3 per cent (3.2%).

Also, the *Nigerian Compass* had more stories sourced through other media publication/news agency than *The Nation*. While *Nigerian Compass* published 3 stories representing 3 per cent, *The Nation* published 2 stories representing 2 per cent.

However, *The Nation* had more stories sourced through reporter's analysis, investigation, no source indicated and others than the *Nigerian Compass*. They followed thus: reporter's analysis- *The Nation* with 11 stories (9 per cent), *Nigerian Compass* with 5 stories (5 per cent); investigation- *The Nation* with 9 stories (7.1 per cent), *Nigerian Compass* with 2 stories (2 per cent); no source indicated- *The Nation* with 19 stories (15 per cent), *Nigerian Compass* with just 1 story (1 per cent); others- *The Nation* with 15 stories (12 per cent), while *Nigerian Compass* had none.

In analyzing the tone of the stories published by the newspapers under study, the following units of analysis were used: positive, negative, neutral and sensational. The findings are represented in the table below

RQ4: Who are the major players covered in the selected newspapers' reports of the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial election?

Major Actors

MAJOR ACTORS	<i>The Nation</i>	<i>Nigerian Compass</i>	TOTAL
INEC	8 (6.3%)	15 (14.6%)	23 (10%)
Aspirants	31 (24.4%)	20 (19.4%)	51 (22.2%)
Government Officials	3 (2.4%)	6 (5.8%)	9 (3.9%)
Political Parties	21 (16.5%)	30 (29.1%)	51 (22.2%)
Political Party's Chieftains	24 (18.9%)	14 (13.6%)	38 (16.5%)
Human Rights/Civil Societies	15 (11.8%)	16 (15.5%)	31 (13.5%)
Others	25 (19.7%)	2 (1.9%)	27 (11.7%)
TOTAL	127	103	230

From the above table, the major actors of the published stories during the period of study were the aspirants and the political parties with a total of 51 stories, representing slightly above 22 per cent (22.2%) respectively. This is followed by political party chieftains with 38 stories representing about 17

per cent (16.5%). Human rights/civil societies followed next with 31 stories representing about 14 per cent (13.5%). While others had 27 stories representing about 12 per cent (11.7%), INEC had 23 stories making one-tenth of the total stories that is (10%). However, stories on government officials were least with 9 stories representing about 4 per cent (3.9%).

In *The Nation*, aspirants topped the list with a total of 31 stories representing 24.4 per cent, followed by others with 25 stories representing about 20 per cent (19.7%). Political parties had 21 stories representing about 17 per cent (16.5%), while human rights/civil societies had 15 stories representing about 12 per cent (11.8%).

Nonetheless, while INEC had 8 stories representing 6.3 per cent, government officials bottomed the table with 3 stories representing 2.4 per cent.

Unlike *The Nation*, in the *Nigerian Compass*, the major actors were the political parties with a total of 30 stories representing slightly above 29 per cent (29.1%). Aspirants followed with total of 20 stories representing 19.4 per cent, even as human rights/civil societies had 16 stories representing about 16 per cent (15.5%).

While INEC had a total of 15 stories representing about 15 per cent (14.6%), political party chieftains had a total of 14 stories representing about 14 per cent (13.6%). Government officials had 6 stories representing about 6 per cent (5.8%) while others birthed at the bottom of the table with just 2 stories representing about 2 per cent (1.9%).

To answer research question four (4) on who are the major players in the report? From the foregoing, it can be deduced that the major players from the published stories during the period of study were the aspirants and political parties, particularly the ACN and its candidate, Akeredolu, LP and its candidate, Mimiko and PDP and its candidate, Oke.

Of the total of 230 stories published by both papers, the aspirants and political parties had a total of 51 stories representing 22.2 percent respectively. This was followed by political party chieftains with a total of 38 stories representing about 17 per cent (16.5%).

Conclusion

This study concludes that *The Nation* and *Nigerian Compass* newspapers on the Ondo State October 20, 2012 gubernatorial elections, the exercise was given prominence and sensationalism abounded as seen in the reports of the two newspapers during the 15-day period under review and to a large extent, it set the agenda for public discourse with a daily reportage of 15 stories on the average and 34 stories on the front page. It can be seen that ownership structure and political affiliation of media proprietors is a dominating feature among the Nigerian press. The study had proven that owners/proprietors influence editorial contents, thus tampering with the editorial independence of the newspapers. While it is evident that the Nigerian press is still divided along partisan politics, a clear testimony of the view of Oso (2006) citing Omu (1978:233), when he said that “from the 1920s when elections into the Legislative Council started, newspapers shifted their focus from that of political group supporters to organs of political parties.”

Also citing Omu (ibid) Oso attested that “even with the advent of responsible government in 1951 and the emergence of modern political parties as well as party controlled administration, old antagonisms were intensified and the atmosphere of politics and press seethed with bitter rivalry and enmity. The verbal combat was so vicious that the press completely immersed in the vortex of partisan politics... were in no position to prepare the people for the challenges of independence and national unity.” With this frailties, the adherence of Nigerian journalists to the '1998 ILORIN DECLARATION' on editorial independence and objectivity is brought into question.

Recommendations

The Nigerian Press Council (NPC), the Nigerian Union of Journalists (NUJ), the Nigerian Guild of Editors (NGE), other professional and mass media regulatory bodies must continue the pursuance for editorial independence and objectivity in the mass media. For the sustainability of a virile democracy, the Nigerian media must encourage issue-based campaigns and not campaigns of calumny and mudslinging. There is also need to regulate the establishment of media organizations to stall the activities of self-serving politicians who establish them to massage their political ego and interest. Journalists who are seen are purveyors of information should focus more on educative stories that will enable the reading electorates make right choices at elections. Fairness, objectivity,

balance and accuracy (FOBA) as a sacrosanct tenets of journalism, must be the watchword of every journalist in this age of mass media proliferation. Journalism should be used to preach national peace and not fueling partisan politics of calumny and hate.

References

- Allen, M., & Casey, M. K. (2007). Effects of Agenda Setting. In R. W. Preiss (Ed.), *Mass Media Effects Research: Advances Through Meta-analysis*. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.
- Cohen, B. C. (1963). *The Press and Foreign Policy*. Princeton: Princeton University Press.
- Daramola, I. (2012). *Introduction to Mass Communication*, 3rd ed. Lagos: Rothan Press Ltd.
- Folarin, B. (1998). *Issues in Applied Communication*. Ibadan: Stirling-Horden Publishers Nig. Ltd.
- Grant, M.A. (1975). "The Nigerian Press and Politics since Independence." Unpublished Ph.D., University of London.
- Hollihan, T. A. (2001). *Uncivil Wars: Political Campaigns in a Media Age*. Boston, MA: Bedford/St. Martins.
- Lindberg, S. I. (2006). *Democracy and Elections in Africa*. Baltimore: The John Hopkins University Press.
- McCombs, M. E., & Shaw, D. L. (1972). The Agenda Setting Function of the Mass Media. *Public Opinion Quarterly*.
- Memedu, B.T. (2009). *Analysis of Fashion Reporting in Selected Nigerian Newspaper*. Unpublished Bsc. Research Project, Lagos State University.
- Nwosu, I. (1996). Role of the Press in Transitory Nigeria. In Dare, O. et al, *Journalism in Nigeria*. Lagos: Cargo Compass Nigeria Ltd.
- Ogunade, Delu (1990). "Media's Best" *African Concord*, October 8th.
- Ojo, E. (2007). *Media Coverage of 2007 Elections: Lessons From 2003*. Election Reporting Resource Handbook for Nigerian Journalists.
- Omu, F.I.A. (1978). *Press and Politics in Nigeria, 1880-1937*. London: Longman Group Limited.
- Oso, L. (2006). "Engineering A Consensus: The Press & Babangida Administration (1985-1993), *Africa Journalism and Communication Review*. Vol 1. No 1.
- Oso, L. (2006). The Nigerian Mass Media and Mass Participation in Politics. *Journal of Philosophy and Development*, Vol. 8, Nos. 1 & 2.
- Oso, L. (2012). *Press and Politics in Nigeria: On Whose Side?* Lagos: Lagos State University.
- Owolabi, T.O. & Achike, C.O. (2011). Professionalism and Ethics in Political Reporting and National Development. *Journalism & Society Journal*,

- Department of Journalism, Lagos State University. Vol.1 No.1, pp 92-113.
- Ridout, T. N., & Mellen, B., Jr. (2007). 'Does the Media Agenda Reflect the Candidates' Agenda? Press/Politics
- Siebert, F. et al. (1956). Four Theories of the Press. Urbana: University of Illinois Press.
- Weaver, D., McCombs, M., & Shaw, D. L. (2004). Agenda-setting Research: Issues, Attributes, and Influences. In Lynda L. Kaid (Ed.), Handbook of Political Communication Research. Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

Online

- Compass Newspaper (2013) Retrieved from <http://www.compassnewspaper.org>. on 19-01-2013
- Independent National Electoral Commission - Nigeria (2013) INEC to conduct Ondo Governorship Election on 20th October. Retrieved from: <http://www.inecnigeria.org/inec-to-conduct-ondo-governorship-election-on-20th-october/> Retrieved on 19-01-2013
- Independent National Electoral Commission - Nigeria (2013) Ondo State Governorship Election Result. Retrieved from: <http://www.inecnigeria.org/ondo-state-governorship-election-result/on19-01-2013>
- National Open University of Nigeria (___) Media and Society. Retrieved from: http://www.nou.edu.ng/noun/NOUN_OCL/pdf/pdf/JLS713%20media%20and%20society.pdf on 19-01-2013.
- Ondo State MOI (2013). Retrieved from: <http://www.ondostatemoi.gov.ng/node/13> on 19-01-2013.
- The Nation Newspaper (2013) About Retrieved from: <http://www.thenationonlineng.net/about.html>. on 2013-01-19
- The Nation Newspaper (2013) Retrieved from: <http://www.thenationonlineng.net> on 19-01-2013
- Wikipedia (2013). History_of_Nigeria. Retrieved from http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/History_of_Nigeria. on 19-01-2013